

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The academic achievement of B.Ed. colleges in Manipur: A comparative study

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Abstract

Teacher Education is the back bone of School Education, which will reform the school education system in the country. In order to check the quality of teacher education being provided in the different Teacher Educational Institutions in Manipur is the need of hour as the academic achievement is the outcomes of educational facility being provided in the colleges. The study will find out the best college, where the quality teacher education being provided, but also, it will suggest the remedial measures in order to improve the quality of teacher education being provided in Manipur.

Keywords: Academic Achievement, B. Ed; Trainees; B.Ed. College; Manipur

1. Introduction

In Common sense parlance, the term “Academic Performance” Can be referred as the extent to which a trainee has achieved His/her educational goals. It is the output/outcome of Education. It is commonly measured by examinations. Hence, Quality of product or output of a training institute can be Determined by its trainees’ academic performance in the public examination or how well a trainee meets standards Set out by the affiliating university and the institution itself. In the 21st century, as career opportunity in the teaching World grows, the importance of prospective teacher trainees doing well in their academic performance has caught Everybody’s attention including those of administrators, Legislators and government education department alike. According to NCTE – 2009, “Teacher education and school Education have a symbiotic relationship and developments in both these sectors mutually reinforce the concerns necessary for qualitative Improvements of the entire spectrum of education including teacher Education as well”. Hence, in teacher training institutes, along with practice teaching, trainees are given knowledge of Different theoretical subjects to form sound educational base.

Significance of the Study: This study will be useful to the teacher educators and teacher trainees as well as the education department, it will be useful for framing curriculum and construction methods that will promote the development of academic achievement of B.Ed. teacher trainees. Achievement means, an accomplishment or proficiency of performance in a given skills or Body or knowledge. Academic achievement is more important for learning and personality development of teacher trainees. Assessing Trainees progress by means of identifying what he has achieved in acquiring skills in academic matters is important as a means of attaining complete realization and it is unique responsibility of institution. Academic achievement also helps to shape the minds of students. Academic achievement is important because it prepares students for future careers. It also allows students to enter competitive fields. Academic achievement is often a sign of a refined intellect, which can help students in all areas of their lives. This study is very significant as which will measures and find out the levels of academic achievement so different B.Ed. colleges in the Manipur. This study will also help to improve the level of academic achievement of trainees of different colleges in Manipur.

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1.1. Definition of the Operational Terms:

- Academic Achievement – It is the extent to which a trainee has achieved their educational goals. For the present study it is considered in terms of marks obtained in final B.Ed. examination conducted by Manipur University for academic in the year 2019 -2021
- **B.Ed.** – It is the Secondary Teacher Education Programme in India. It is the mandatory requirement for a graduate or Post graduate to complete this course in order to be a Secondary teacher/graduate teacher.
- **Trainees** -Trainee-teacher is a student enrolled for the professional Degree of Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.). S/he has opted to regularly attend college and practice how to prepare and teach a well-planned, good and effective lesson by learner-Centric and interactive methodology.
- **B.Ed. College** : The colleges offering B.Ed. course located in Manipur State.
- **Manipur**: One of the states among North East States of India.

1.2. Objectives of the study:

- To find out the overall academic achievement of B.Ed. Trainees of all Teacher Educational Institutions in Manipur
- To compare the overall academic achievement of all B. Ed male trainees is higher than female B. Ed colleges under Manipur university
- All colleges have equal numbers of position holders in the university examination
- The overall academic achievement of all B. Ed male trainees division wise is higher than female trainee of B. Ed colleges under Manipur university

1.3. Hypothesis of the Study

- The overall academic achievement of B. Ed trainees of all B. Ed colleges under Manipur University is High
- The overall academic achievement of male trainee is higher than female trainee of all B. Ed colleges under Manipur university
- All colleges have equal numbers of position holders in the university examination
- The overall academic achievement of all B. Ed male trainees division wise is higher than female B. Ed colleges under Manipur university

1.4. Delimitation of the Study

- The present study has geographically limited to B. Ed Colleges of Teacher Educational Institution in Imphal District, Manipur.
- The present study has confined only to 4 (four) B.Ed. Colleges of Teacher Educational Institution within Imphal District, Manipur.

2. Review of the related literature (International Level)

1. Keith Curry 1992, Quality library media programs affect academic achievements university of Denver. The evidence is mounting, By early 2000, researches affiliated with the library research service of the Colorado state library and the university of Denver had completed four state wide studies on the impact of school library media programs on the academic achievement of U.S. public schools. The findings of the study were: (1) All of the recent studies of the impact of school library media programs of academic achievement provide evidence to support several common findings. (2) Professionally trained and Credential school library media specialists do make a difference that affects Students performance on achievement tests. (3) Library media specialists cannot perform their jobs effectively unless they have support staff who free them from routine tasks and enable them to participate in a variety of one and group, meeting outside the library media centre. (2) Yi-Chen Hung, Pey- Yan Liou, (2007): Examining the relationship between student academic achievement and self-concept in the I/E, BFLPE, and combined models- Evidence from East Asian countries in TIMSS 2007, Ph.D. National Central university, paper presented at the 5th IEA International Research Conference Singapore-June 26-28, 2013. The theoretical hypothesis were Student math score has a significantly positive relationship with math self-concept, but has a significantly negative relationship with science self-concept. Student science score has a significantly positive relationship with science self-concept, but has a significantly negative relative relationship with math self-concept. School math score has a significantly negative relationship with student math self-concept. School science score has a significantly negative relationship with student science self-concept.

3. Tohid Moradi Sheykhjan, Dr Kamran Jabari and Rajeswari 2014: The primary purpose of this study was to determine the influence of self-esteem on academic achievement among high school students in Miandoab city of Iran. *The major objectives of the study were:* To find out the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement of high school students. To find out the relationship between self-esteem with respect to gender among high school students. The major findings of the study were: The results of the findings of the study: A very high correlation between academic achievement and self-esteem and concluded that there is significant positive correlation between self-esteem and academic achievement. (4) Deri Indrahadi, Amika Wardana 2020: The study aimed to examine the effect of socio-demographic, student and school factors on the academic achievement of high school students in Indonesia. The study run multiple regression analysis to examine the influences of their parents socio-demographic, students and other school-related factors on their academic achievements during their school years. As the results, it was revealed that the socio-demographic factors, students and schools predict significantly academic achievement of students in Indonesia. The results provided feedback to students and parents, schools and education policymaking in improving student academic achievement. (5) Shahrzad Elahi Motlah, Kouros Amrai, Mohammad Javad Yazdani Haitham Altaib: *The aim of the current study:* To investigate the relation between self-efficacy and academic achievement in high school students. To measure achievement score grade point average in classes was used. To analyse data correlation coefficient and regression analysis was used. *The major findings:* The analysis data revealed that self-evaluation, self-directing and self-regulation are correlated with academic achievement. Among all variables entered in the equation model only self-evaluation and self-regulation model explaining 10 percent variance of academic achievement in two steps. Self-efficacy is a considerable factor in academic achievement.

2.1. Some of the Related Literatures Studies in India:

(1) Desai, S.D., 1979, conducted on a study of classroom Ethos, pupils' motivation and academic achievement, Ph. D. Edu., MSU. *The major objectives were:* To study the level of classroom climates and its components. To measure pupils' motivation, academic achievement and non-academic achievement. To study the relationship between classroom climate, pupils' motivation, academic and Non-academic achievement and socio-economic status and to prepare profile with respect to classroom climate, pupils' motivation and their achievement. The major findings were: The level of classroom climate was positively related of pupils' motivation and their academic achievement. Pupils' academics motivation were positively related to their academic achievement. Socio-economic status has no relationship with pupils' classroom climate or pupils' motivation or with academic achievement. Non-academic achievement had no relationship with classroom climate and pupils' motivation. Boys were higher than girls in the level of classroom climate, pupils academic and achievement, boys score higher mean scores of classroom climates, pupils' motivation and academic achievement than mixed and girls. (2) SCERT, Andhra Pradesh, (1981), Evaluation of In-Service Training Programme for Primary Teachers in the selected Government and Aided Teacher Training Institutions. *The objectives of the study were:* (a) To evaluate the administration aspects of the function of the science teaching course for primary teachers, (b) To evaluate the academic aspect, that is, the schedule of work and activities acquired during the in-service training programme, and (c) To study the relevance of the course content to the objectives of the in-service training programme. The findings of the study were: (a) Adequate persons of the course felt that Adequate staff was not there, Individual attention was not possible in the course, Science consultants were not provided, and There was no books through which modern concepts could be developed (b) The teacher educators laid more stress on pupil participation in the classes, (c) The laboratory techniques employed during the training programme were quite useful but could not be practiced in the schools (3) Srivastava, Kanti Mohan, (1982), Effectiveness of the Teacher Education Programme, Ph. D. Edu., Avadh U., *The main objectives of the study were:* (a) To study the actual position of resources, existing conditions and working of the teacher education programme, (b) To study the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the programmes and product, (c) To study the effect of the programme on teaching aptitude of student-teachers, (d) To study opinions regarding quality of sufficiency of existing conditions and working of the programme from the point of view of organization professional education of secondary teachers, (e) To study opinions regarding utility of the programmes from the point of view of the teacher job, and (f) To ascertain the most desirable changes needed for making the programme effective. *The main findings were:* (a) The ten colleges having teacher education department were unequal in size and facilities and none were initially opened with the intension of providing facilities for teacher education. The colleges were on the government grant list: hence there was no problem of staff salary payment, except SC and ST student-trainees, all others were required to pay fees.

2.2. Conclusion

It can be concluded that the topic of the study is new area which is not conducted by anyone before, which will help us to solve the problems of academic achievements of B.Ed. colleges in Manipur.

2.3. Method of the present study

In the present study the investigator has been adopted historical method cum descriptive survey method was employed in the collection of achievement record of the examination results of the four B. Ed colleges of teachers training in Manipur during 2019- 2021.

Population Of The Study : In the present study, all the four B. Ed colleges in Manipur specially within Imphal area have been taken as the sample population of the study as there as any no selection of sample of the whole unit of the of the population. The whole unit of population have been taken as sample of the study. But the results of only three consecutive Year, viz.,2019, 2020, and 2021 are taken as a sample of the Teachers trainee result

2.4. Sample of the study

The investigator used stratified random sampling technique for selecting a sample of only four B. Ed colleges examinations results during 2019 to 2021 in Imphal area.

Name of the four B. Ed colleges	
Department Of Teacher Education Manipur University	Kanan Devi College Of Teacher Education
D.M College Of Teacher Education	R.K. Sanatombi Devi College Of Teacher Education

2.5. Tools of the Present Study

In the present study, the investigator used the records, and reports both published and unpublished regarding teacher education. The investigator visited all the four B. Ed colleges to collect records of achievement of the examination results from the college offices. He has visited Manipur University to collect the overall results of examination of B. Ed. Course and Annual Reports published by the University.

2.6. Statistical Technique Used

In the present study, the investigator has employed percentage and graph as a method of statistical technique for analysis of the collected data:

Percentage and Graphical representation

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Hypothesis-1: The overall academic achievement of trainees of all B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University is high

Table 1 Overall academic achievement of trainees of all B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University.

Year	No. of appeared	No. of passed	Passed %	No. of failed	Failed %
2019	1056	892	84.47	164	15.53
2020	1270	1199	94.41	071	05.59
2021	1401	1041	74.30	360	25.69
Sum	3727	3132	253.18	595	46.81
Mean	1243	1044	84.40	199	15.60

Figure 1 Overall academic achievement of B.Ed. trainees of all B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University

Interpretation

The table No. 1 and figure No: 1 reveals the year wise academic achievement of the B.Ed. trainees of four B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University during 2019-2021 for a period of three years. It shows the number of candidates passed and overall passes percentage. It is noticed that the pass percentage was lowest in 2021, (74.30%) and highest in 2020, (94.41%). In 2019 the lowest number of students 1056 appeared for the B.Ed. examination and the highest number of students 1401 appeared for the B.Ed. examination in 2021.

The highest and the lowest level of failed students are 05.59% in 2020 and 25.69% in 2021.

The average pass and fail percentage for the last three years are 84.40% (1044 out of 1243) and 15.60 % (199 out of 1243). From this we learnt that around 199 students of four B.Ed. Colleges are failed in B.Ed. Examination conducted by Manipur University.

Conclusion: It can be concluded that the overall average academic achievement of all the students of B.Ed. Examination conducted by Manipur University in the last three years i.e., 2019-2021 among the four B.Ed. colleges is found as 84.40%. It is therefore the first hypothesis of the present study that was constructed for testing “The overall academic achievement of B.Ed. students of all B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University is high” is accepted as the overall academic achievement is 84.40% and failed percentage is only 15.60%.

3.2. Hypothesis-2 The overall academic achievement of male trainees is higher than female trainees of all B.Ed. colleges under Manipur University.

Table 2 Overall academic achievement of male and female trainees of B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University

Year	Number of student teacher appeared			Number of student teacher passed			Pass %		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	male	Female	Total
2019	339	717	1056	282	610	892	83.18	85.07	84.47
2020	421	849	1270	398	801	1199	94.53	94.34	94.41
2021	456	945	1401	321	720	1041	70.39	76.19	74.30
Total	1216	2511	3727	1001	2131	3132	248.1	255.6	253.18
Average	405	837	1243	333.67	710.33	1044	82.7	85.2	84.39

Figure 2 The overall academic achievement of male and female trainees of B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University.

Interpretation: The highest pass percentage for female in the three years (2019-2021) is 94.34% in 2020 and lowest pass percentage is 76.19% in the year 2021. However, the average pass percentage in the last three years for female is 85.07%.in the year 2019.

The highest pass percentage for male in the three years (2019-2021) is 94.53% in 2020 and lowest pass percentage is 70.39 in the year 2021. However, the average pass percentage in the last three years for male is 83.18%.

The average pass percentage in the last three years for male and female is 82.7% and 85.2% respectively. The total average for both male and female is 84.39%. Conclusion: The overall pass percentage of male B.Ed. trainees (82.7%) of four colleges is lower than the academic achievement of female B.Ed. Trainees (85.2%).

It is therefore the 2nd hypothesis of the present study that was constructed for testing “The overall academic achievement of male trainees is higher than female of all B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University” is rejected as the overall academic achievement of female trainees is higher than that of male trainees.

3.3. Hypothesis-3: All colleges have equal numbers of position holders (Rank holders and Gold medalist) in the university examination

Table 3 Overall academic achievement in terms of Rank holders trainees of B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University

Year	MU	RKSDCE	KDMCE	DMCTE
2019	01	01	00	00
2020	00	00	00	00
2021	01	00	01	00

Figure 3 Overall academic achievement in terms of Rank holders trainees of B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University.

Interpretation: The college which produced number of position holders in the last three years is (1) Department of Teacher Education Manipur university, (2) R.K. Sanatombi Devi college of Teacher Education and (3) Kanan Devi College of Teacher Education, Pangei. (2019-2, 2021-1, total: 3). Whereas (1) D.M College of Teacher Education, Imphal, (2) RK. Sanatombi Devi College of Education, Imphal, (3) Kanan Devi Memorial College of Teacher Education, Pangei, and (4) Department of Teacher Education Manipur University did not produced position holders in the year 2020.

Conclusion: It can be concluded that there is no equal number of position holders produced by four B.Ed. Colleges. It is therefore the 3rd hypothesis “All colleges have equal numbers of position holders (Rank holders and Gold medallist) in the university examination” is rejected as there is no equal number of position holders produced by four colleges.

3.4. Hypotheses 4: The overall academic achievement of all male trainees in division wise is higher than female trainees of B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University.

Table 4 Overall academic achievement in terms of division wise among trainees of B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University

Year	Appeared		1st division		%		2 nd Division		%	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
2019	159	331	147	328	92.45	99.09	12	03	07.54	00.90
2020	141	392	125	382	88.65	97.44	16	10	11.34	02.55
2021	187	318	175	313	93.58	98.42	12	05	06.41	01.57
Average	162.33	347	149	341	91.56	98.31	13.33	06	08.43	01.67

Figure 4 Overall academic achievement in terms of division wise among trainees of B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University

Interpretation: The highest pass percentage for 1st Division female in the three years (2019-2021) is 99.09% in 2019 and lowest pass percentage for 1st Division female is 97.44% in the year 2020. However, the average pass percentage in the last three years for female 1st division is 98.42%.in the year 2021.

The highest pass percentage for male 1st division in the three years (2019-2021) is 93.58% in 2021 and lowest pass percentage of male 1st division is 88.65 in the year 2020. However, the average pass percentage in the last three years for male 1st division is 92.45%.

The average pass percentage in the last three years for male 1st division and female 1st division is 91.56.% and 98.31.2% respectively.

Interpretation: The highest pass percentage for 2ndDivision male in the three years (2019-2021) is 11.34% in 2020 and lowest pass percentage for 2nd Division male is 6.41.% in the year 2021. However, the average pass percentage in the last three years for male 2nd division is 7.54%.

The highest pass percentage for female 2nd division in the three years (2019-2021) is 2.55% in 2020 and lowest pass percentage of female 2nd division is 0.90 in the year 2019. However, the average pass percentage in the last three years for male 2nd division is 1.57%.

The average pass percentage in the last three years for male 2nd division and female 2nd division is 8.43% and 1.67 % respectively

It is therefore the 4th hypothesis of the present study that was constructed for testing “The overall academic achievement of all B.Ed. male student division wise is higher than female B.Ed. Colleges of all colleges under Manipur University” is rejected as the overall academic achievement female is higher than male.

3.5. Main Findings of the study

The overall average academic achievement of all the students of B.Ed. Examination conducted by Manipur University in the last three years i.e., 2019-2021 among the four B.Ed. colleges is found as 84.40%. It is therefore the first hypothesis of the present study that was constructed for testing “The overall academic achievement of B.Ed. students of all B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University is high” is accepted as the overall academic achievement is 84.40% and failed percentage is only 15.60%.

The overall pass percentage of male B.Ed. trainees (82.7%) of four colleges is lower than the academic achievement of female B.Ed. Trainees (85.2%). It is therefore the 2nd hypothesis of the present study that was constructed for testing “The overall academic achievement of male trainees is higher than female of all B.Ed. Colleges under Manipur University” is rejected as the overall academic achievement of female trainees is higher than that of male trainees.

There is no equal number of position holders produced by four B.Ed. Colleges. It is therefore the 3rd hypothesis “All four colleges have equal numbers of position holders (Rank holders and Gold medallist) in the university examination” is rejected as there is no equal number of position holders produced by four colleges.

The highest pass percentage for 1st Division female in the three years (2019-2021) is 99.09% in 2019 and lowest pass percentage for 1st Division female is 97.44% in the year 2020. However, the average pass percentage in the last three years for female 1st division is 98.42%.in the year 2021.The highest pass percentage for male 1st division in the three years (2019-2021) is 93.58% in 2021 and lowest pass percentage of male 1st division is 88.65 in the year 2020. However, the average pass percentage in the last three years for male 1st division is 92.45%.The average pass percentage in the last three years for male 1st division and female 1st division is 91.56.% and 98.31.2% respectively.

The highest pass percentage for 2ndDivision male in the three years (2019-2021) is 11.34% in 2020 and lowest pass percentage for 2nd Division male is 6.41.% in the year 2021. However, the average pass percentage in the last three years for male 2nd division is 7.54%.The highest pass percentage for female 2nd division in the three years (2019-2021) is 2.55% in 2020 and lowest pass percentage of female 2nd division is 0.90 in the year 2019. However, the average pass percentage in the last three years for male 2nd division is 1.57%. The average pass percentage in the last three years for male 2nd division and female 2nd division is 8.43% and 1.67 % respectively

It is therefore the 4th hypothesis of the present study that was constructed for testing “The overall academic achievement of all B.Ed. male student division wise is higher than female B.Ed. Colleges of all colleges under Manipur University” is rejected as the overall academic achievement female is higher than male.

3.6. Remedial Measures for further improvement subject to main findings of the study

The overall Academic Achievement of trainees of B. Ed Colleges in Manipur comes 84.40% only which is not so high and 15.60% of the total sample are failed. It is therefore more improvement is necessary as far as the academic achievement of B. Ed trainees in Manipur to reach optimum level.

The overall pass percentage of male B.Ed. trainees (82.7%) of four colleges is lower than the academic achievement of female B.Ed. Trainees (85.2%) as there is not much difference between male and female trainees of B. Ed of four colleges in pass% and the percentage is low as it does not reach 100%. So, improvement should be made to both male and female trainees to reach the optimum level

It can be concluded that there is no equal number of position holders produced by four B.Ed. Colleges. It is therefore the 3rd hypothesis “All four colleges have equal numbers of position holders (Rank holders and Gold medalist) in the

university examination” is rejected as there is no equal number of position holders produced by four colleges. So, improvement should be required to all the four B. Ed colleges as rank holders are very low for all the four colleges during 2019 – 2021.

The average pass percentage in the last three years for male 1st division and female 1st division is 91.56.% and 98.31.2% respectively. The average pass percentage in the last three years for male 2nd division and female 2nd division is 8.43% and 1.67 % respectively. It is therefore more improvement is necessary for both male and female trainees of B. Ed in order to pass all trainees in 1st division

3.7. General Suggestion for the improvement of academic achievements among the trainees of B.Ed. colleges in Manipur:

- To maintain good academic calendar.
- Regular and frequent inspection to the college by the concern authority.
- Well-built infrastructure in each college.
- To give the financial support from government side to the schools.
- To develop the better relationships between the trainee and teacher.
- To impart good teaching methods in the teaching-learning process
- Timely notification for the modifications of syllabus should be notified to the trainee in time. 8. To modify the texts from time to time and to make available to market in time for the quality as per NCERT.
- To include the practical oriented syllabus.
- To follow CCE pattern in evaluation process. 11. To develop blue print of the examination question.
- To organized the co-curricular activities annually without fail.
- To organize the workshops, seminars and orientations programs for trainees
- Value education should be taught to the trainees

4. Conclusion

There is need of improvement of B.Ed. academic achievement of Teacher Educational Institutions in Manipur in terms of overall, sex wise, division wise as the academic achievement level of B.Ed. colleges in different areas is not up to the maximum level. So that, Quality teacher education can be provided in the state as well as Nationwide.

Compliance with ethical standards

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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